

Applying Machine Learning to Natural Product Chemical Space

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Abstract. The chemical space spanned by natural products and natural product-like compounds is a key focus for many drug discovery campaigns, representing almost a third of recently approved small molecule drugs [1]. Natural products tend to be larger and more complex than purely synthetic compounds, encompassing a wide range of chemical scaffolds, and their natural origin and evolutionary optimization means that they represent a different molecular arsenal to what is typically explored in a synthetic chemistry effort. Combined with the presence of biologically relevant pharmacophores and their specific spatial arrangement due to the higher number of sp^3 hybridized carbons and chiral centres, natural products represent a very promising source of novel candidates for small molecule drugs. However, while the distinction of natural and synthetic compounds based on chemical structure has been well studied [2], how best to account for the different molecular characteristics of natural and synthetic molecules, especially given the relatively low abundance of natural products in many freely available datasets, remains an open question. This is particularly relevant when training and applying machine learning models specifically to natural product chemical space [3]. In this work, we investigate a range of different machine learning approaches to represent, sample, model and obtain predictions for the biological activity of natural products against different protein targets. We demonstrate that machine learning models trained on synthetic compounds often do not extrapolate well to natural product space. To address this, we explore different sampling approaches which can be applied to curate a more suitable training set for natural product predictive models from the available, largely synthetic, compound datasets. We benchmark these approaches across a number of datasets for a range of disease-relevant targets. Whilst we observe target specific trends in many cases, indicating that algorithms are best optimised for a specific drug discovery application, we were able to identify more general trends and highlight more robust approaches for successfully building and deploying natural product focused predictive models. This will help tailor machine learning models to natural product chemical space and thereby enable the scientific community to more successfully identify natural product-like compounds as future drugs to treat diseases.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Natural Products, Drug Discovery

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